

Effect of Heat Treatment on the Leaching Characteristics of Alkali Borosilicate Glasses

N. K. MITRA*, S. R. VASISTHA, A. C. DAS and A. BASUMAJUMDAR

Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

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Effect of heat treatment at 450, 500, 550 and 600° of low melting alkali borosilicate glasses of size fractions, -30+60, -60+80, -80+120 mesh, on the leaching characteristics, has been studied by estimating SiO₂, B₂O₃, Na₂O, K₂O, MgO, CaO and BaO leached out in isothermal conditions. Heat treatment improves chemical durability of both soda-lime-silica and potash-baria glasses by separation of some soluble phases followed by formation of some stable phases at higher temperature.

CHEMICAL durability of glass is directly related to the migration of diffusible ions from the glass structure. This migration of ions from the glass structure depends on the composition of the glass, nature, concentration and duration of leaching solution in contact with it, temperature as well as pressure. Two-phase sodium borosilicate glasses were studied by Kiyohisha *et al.*¹ to correlate the time and temperature of heat-treatment of the original glass with the rate of acid leaching. Dubravo² studied the effect of heat treatment on the chemical durability of glass. Sen *et al.*³ studied the net effect of annealing on the chemical durability of glass. Zaiouts and Rogozhim⁴ observed that the chemical stability of pyrex glass in acids is a function of heat treatment.

Since the utility of a glass depends primarily on its chemical durability, the present investigation has been undertaken to study the effect of heat treatment of low-melting alkali borosilicate glass on the leaching characteristics.

Experimental

Raw materials selected for the preparation of glasses, boric acid, borax, sodium carbonate, potassium carbonate, magnesium carbonate, calcium carbonate, barium carbonate were of AnalaR grade and glass sand was from Allahabad. Glass sand was received in very fine state of subdivisions (particle size < 100 mesh). It was dispersed in a large bulk of water in presence of sodium hexametaphosphate (0.002 mol dm⁻³) for dispersion of adherent clay particles. Suspended clay particles were removed by

repeated sedimentation technique. Finally, sand was leached with 6 N HCl to remove iron and iron salts followed by filtration, repeated washing with hot distilled water until free from chloride and was dried at 110°. The materials were accurately weighed as per the batch compositions, precalcined and the glasses were prepared in a gas-fired furnace at 1400° by double melting technique. The prepared glasses were ground carefully, sieved to -30+60, -60+80, and -80+120 mesh size fractions and stored in air-tight bottles. The perfect glassy nature of all the glasses was confirmed by X-ray analysis. Because of similar nature, a typical X-ray analysis of glass sample no. G₃ is shown in Fig. 1. All the glasses were analysed for SiO₂, B₂O₃, Na₂O, K₂O, MgO, CaO and BaO by standard chemical methods^{5,6}.

For heat-treatment operation, the glass sample (2 g) of a particular size fraction was taken in a platinum crucible placed in an electrically operated muffle furnace. The temperatures of heat-treatment were 450, 500, 550 and 600°. The rate of rise of temperature was strictly maintained at 5° min⁻¹. The glass was soaked at the final temperature for 4 h, then taken out, cooled and kept in air-tight bottles. Exactly 1 g of the heat-treated sample was used for leaching with distilled water at 50°. After leaching, the constituents in the aqueous phase were determined by the standard chemical methods mentioned earlier.

Results and Discussion

The chemical compositions of all the glasses were determined (Table 1)⁷.

Fig. 1. X-Ray photograph of glass sample no. G₁.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE MELTED GLASSES

Glass sample no.	Chemical composition (mole percent)						
	SiO ₂	B ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	MgO	CaO	BaO
G ₁	70.52	19.48	9.85	—	—	—	—
G ₂	70.38	13.75	15.75	—	—	—	—
G ₃	70.41	9.85	19.62	—	—	—	—
G ₄	70.30	13.80	9.84	—	6.02	—	—
G ₅	70.28	13.78	9.83	—	—	6.05	—
G ₆	70.38	13.75	9.85	—	—	—	5.95
G ₇	70.28	13.68	—	9.85	—	—	—
G ₈	70.26	13.85	—	15.80	—	—	—
G ₉	70.25	9.90	—	19.70	—	—	—
G ₁₀	70.22	13.82	—	9.80	6.02	—	—
G ₁₁	70.20	13.85	—	9.82	—	6.05	—
G ₁₂	70.25	13.80	—	9.80	—	—	6.00

The heat treatment was carried out with (-30+60) mesh glass powder and the results are shown in Figs. 2-5.

From Fig. 2 it appears that upto 450° there was virtually very little reaction with the soda glasses following which a sharp peak was obtained at 550°. This was common to all soda glasses. The dissolution of silica was then appreciably reduced when

Fig. 2

the glasses were heat-treated at 600°. In all cases, it was lower than the value obtained without heat-treatment at a specific temperature. Same type of leaching curves for silica as a function of temperature of heat-treatment were obtained for potash glasses only with the difference that the peak temperature shifted to 500° for soda glasses. At the peak point, the order of the glasses with respect to leaching of silica for soda and potash glasses respectively may be written as,

$$G_4 > G_5 > G_6 = G_3 \text{ and } G_7 > G_{11} > G_{12} > G_{10}$$

B₂O₃ leaching curves (Fig. 3) were different from that of silica, although glass sample no. G₃ showed a small peak at 450°. All the soda glasses except G₅ showed a sharp fall in B₂O₃ extraction from 450°. Rapid stabilisation of B₂O₃ with temperature of heat treatment was observed with all potash glasses when a sharp decrease was noticed

Fig. 3

from the original point upto 550° followed by another increase. In case of soda glasses no such increase was observed at 600°. The order of the soda glasses with respect to B₂O₃ extraction of the final point of heat treatment may be written as G₅ > G₄ > G₆ = G₃. The comparative difference of B₂O₃ leaching from soda glass was negligible with that

of potash glasses at the final temperature of heat-treatment. The order of the potash glasses at the minimum point of extraction, i.e. at 550°, may be written as $G_{11} > G_{10} > G_7 > G_{12}$.

Gradual decrease of R_2O (Na_2O/K_2O) extraction on progressive heat-treatment of glasses was observed (Fig. 4) with all the soda glasses following the same nature. Only glass no G_3 showed same difference at 550°, where a sharp peak was noted.

Fig 4

Sharp decrease was observed from 450°. For potash glasses the nature of the curves was similar, all showing a peak at 550°. Above the peak point the amount of extraction was same for all glasses except G_{10} . Similarly at the final point of heat treatment the difference was minimum except G_{13} .

G_6 and G_{12} (BaO substituted glasses) showed same type of curves, a decrease followed by an increase at 550° and again a decrease (Fig. 5). At the peak point the BaO extraction was maximum with soda glass. Flat diffuse type of curve was observed with G_{11} . At the final point of heat treatment the order of RO extraction may be represented as $G_6 > G_5 > G_{12} > G_{11}$.

Thus, though the extraction of BaO was greater than CaO , the presence of BaO stabilised the other

Fig. 5

components to a greater degree. Under the conditions of heat-treatment, some heterogeneity occurred in the composition of the glasses, which is reflected in their leaching behaviour. The heat-treated glasses were subjected to X-ray analysis (Fig. not shown) which did not reveal any evidence of development of crystalline phase. This clearly indicates that the heat-treatment led to some instability in the glass composition leading to separation of phases, which were glassy (amorphous) in nature—one being rich in alkalis where as the other rich in silica.

Conclusion : (i) The dissolution of silica was lower than the value obtained without heat-treatment. (ii) Unlike silica, temperature of heat-treatment has a positive effect on the stabilisation of B_2O_3 of the borosilicate glasses. (iii) The modifier oxides can be stabilised or expelled from the structure depending on the temperature of heat-treatment and all the glasses followed more or less the same course of transformation. Thus, it is concluded that both soda lime and potash-baria glasses improved the chemical durability, though not proportionately to the temperature of heat treatment as compared with the other glasses. From the nature of the curves it appears that at the peak point there is separation of some soluble phases (indicated by increase of corrosion) followed by formation of some stable phases at higher temperature.

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